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BACHELOR OF LAWS

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BARAZA YURI J.

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**A CRITIQUE OF THE ADEQUACY OF KENYA'S LEGAL
FRAMEWORK FOR SOCIAL MEDIA REGULATION DURING
ELECTIONS**

**A DISSERTATION PRESENTED TO THE FACULTY OF LAW FOR
THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE
AWARD OF THE DEGREE OF BACHELOR OF LAWS (LL. B) OF
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SUPERVISOR: PROF. PETER A. WASAMBA

DECLARATION

I, **YURI J. BARAZA**, declare that this is my original work and that it has not been submitted to any university or institution of higher learning for the award of a Diploma, Degree or Post-Graduate qualification.

Signed..... Date.....

YURI J. BARAZA

Signed..... Date.....

PROFESSOR PETER A. WASAMBA

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my grandparents, the late Nathan Makokha and the late Racheal Nabifwo Makokha who could have become great lawyers had they had the same opportunity that I have had.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ARPA	Advanced Research Projects Agency
BAKE.....	Bloggers Association of Kenya
IAPs.....	Internet Access Providers
ICCPR	International Convention on Civil and Political Rights
ICTs.....	Information and Communication Technologies
KANU	Kenya African National Union
KCA	Kenya Communications Act
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
UN.....	United Nations
UNHR.....	United Nations Human Rights Council
US.....	United States
UK.....	United Kingdom

LIST OF CONSTITUTIONS AND STATUTES

The Constitution of Kenya 2010.

Media Council Act, 2013

The Armed Forces Act, CAP 199;

The Books and Newspapers Act, CAP 111;

The Chief's Authority Act CAP 128;

The Copyright Act, CAP 130;

The Defamation Act, CAP 36;

The Films and Stage Plays Act, CAP 22;

The Official Secrets Act, CAP 187

The Police Act, CAP 84;

The Preservation of Public Security Act, CAP 57;

The Public Order Act, CAP 56;

The Kenya Broadcasting Act, CAP 221;

The Kenya Information and Communications Act, 2013;

The Media Act, 2013.

LIST OF CITED CASES

Bloggers Association of Kenya (BAKE) v Attorney General & 3 others; Article 19 East Africa & Another (Interested Parties) [2020] eKLR

Chavunduka v Minister of Home Affairs (2000), The Supreme Court of Zimbabwe

Geoffrey Andare v Attorney General & 2 others (2016), eKLR.

Jacqueline Okuta & another v Attorney General & 2 others [2017] eKLR

LIST OF INTERNATIONAL AND REGIONAL INSTRUMENTS

1. African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights ("Banjul Charter"), 27 June 1981.
2. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 16 December 1966, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 999, p. 171.
3. International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 16 December 1966, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 993, p.3.
4. Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 10 December 1948, 217 A (III).

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ABSTRACT

Kenya experienced the negative impact of fake news during both the 2013 and 2017 general elections. As a consequence, the government has resorted to the use of draconian and antiquated laws such as the Penal Code and/or enacted some new laws aimed at regulating social media to tame the menace. The Constitution of Kenya on the other hand guarantees fundamental freedoms of expression, free media and access to information. This study argues that these fundamental freedoms face the danger of violation through the kind of legal regulatory mechanisms being deployed by government. This study set out to examine the adequacy of the regulatory regime in place for regulation of social media especially during elections, and whether it is suitable in upholding these fundamental freedoms. The study used qualitative research methodology, specifically doctrinal and comparative methods for data collection. For theoretical framework, the study adopted the proportionality theory due to its potential in resolution of conflicts between a right and a competing right or interest, which is at the core of this study. It was found that legal approaches to regulation of fake news, especially criminalization, is counter-productive in a democracy. It was further established that other jurisdictions such as Singapore, Germany, Australia and Canada have preferred non-legal approaches such as self-regulation of social media which could be useful to Kenya. The study recommends a multi-pronged approach in order to effectively safeguard against the impacts of ill-speech. Specific recommendations are that Kenya should have better fact-checkers and authorities committed to respond to public interest; Kenya should adopt limited but necessary legislative support to help generate consensus with a much more effective regulatory mechanism; and that the Government should put in place a legal framework against problematic social media content and in any such strategy, the tech platforms are bound to play the biggest role.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background

Social media has become the most popular and most used mode of media communication in recent history. Many claims are made about the democratizing power of new media. Social media is considered to contribute to government accountability, human rights activism, the development of civil society and practices of citizenship. In terms of accountability and transparency, it is increasingly difficult for governments to hide or manipulate information or to act inconsistently with citizen concerns. The use of mobile phones and the Internet, for example, allow for news of any inappropriate government actions to quickly reach the public and to be challenged. It also allows for people to follow decision-making processes and discuss issues of common concern.¹ The health and vigor of any society depends on good governance, i.e., well-functioning public institutions. Equally important, however, is the ability of citizens to express their views and communicate with each other in the public sphere without hindrance. This happens in an environment that inspires confidence in social institutions and mutual trust among citizens. This in turn constitutes the basis for freedom of expression, for both individuals and various interest groups. Such a ‘climate’ is largely a consequence of the existence of a variety of independent media.²

The phenomenal increase of social media use has, however, come with the problem of purveying fake news, which has been blamed for its negative influence on elections.³ The consequence of the influence of fake news on the electoral process was seriously experienced during the 2013 election.⁴ A lot of misleading information on different sides of the political divide was allegedly

¹ Christa Odinga. Use of New Media during the Kenya Elections. Master’s Thesis submitted to the Department of Informatics and Media at Uppsala University, in June 2013, in order to obtain a Master’s Degree in Social Science with a specialization in Media and Communication Studies. P 12.

² Ulla Carlsson and Lennart Weibull. Freedom of Expression in the Digital Media Culture. A study of public opinion in Sweden. Printed by Ale Tryckteam AB, Bohus, Sweden, 2018 p 11

³ Nanjala Nyabola. Digital Democracy, Analogue politics/How the Internet Era is Transforming Politics in Kenya. Zedbooks. CPI Group (UK) Ltd, Croydon p79.

⁴ Ibid

circulated.⁵ As a consequence of the negative effect of fake news, Kenya has enacted laws to regulate social media in order to curb the negative influence of fake news. In other cases, the country has used the existing legislation to regulate traditional media, such as the Penal Code and defamation laws.⁶ However, critics like Nanjala Nyabola;⁷ Abdulmalik Sugow;⁸ Patrick Mutahi and Brian Kimari⁹ among others, argue that the laws to regulate social media have the potential to cause an infringement of media freedom, freedom of expression and access to information.¹⁰

The Constitution of Kenya recognizes the importance of media freedom and in fact, upholds media freedom, including social media, under Article 34. The Constitution guarantees the freedom and independence of all types of media, including social media.¹¹ Freedom of expression is enabled by free media and the free flow of information. Freedom of expression has also been recognized in international human rights law as an important human right in a democratic dispensation which is essential for society to be autonomous. It is guaranteed in Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, as well as in the International Convention of Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR).¹²

Moreover, the Constitution of Kenya, under Article 24, provides for the general limitation clause regarding provisions under the Bill of Rights. Thus, for a right under the Constitution to be limited, the limitation has to be reasonable, justifiable and provided for in legislation. The Article states that a freedom can be limited by law when that limitation is reasonable and justifiable in an open and democratic society based on human dignity, equality and freedom.¹³ Therefore, it is of utmost importance to ensure that media freedom, including social media in Kenya is not curtailed in any

⁵ Patrick Mutahi and Brian Kimari. *The Impact of Social Media and Digital Technology on Electoral Violence in Kenya*. Institute of Development Studies 2017 p 6.

⁶ Ibid

⁷ Nanjala Nyabola, n. 2 p 79

⁸ Abdulmalik Sugow. *The Right to be Wrong: Examining the (Im) possibilities of Regulating Fake News while Preserving the Freedom of Expression in Kenya*. *Strathmore Law Review*, June 2019, p 21.

⁹ Patrick Mutahi and Brian Kimari, n. 4 p 6.

¹⁰ Patrick Mutahi and Brian Kimari, n 4 p 6.

¹¹ Article 34 (1), Constitution of Kenya (2010)

¹² Fredrick Wilson and Muhammad A Umar. *The Effect of Fake News on Nigeria's Democracy within the Premise of Freedom of Expression*. *Global Media Journal*. <https://www.globalmediajournal.com/peer-reviewed/the-effect-of-fake-news-on-nigeriasndemocracy-within-the-premise-of-freedom-ofnexpression-87578.html>. P 2.

¹³ Other factors to be considered when limiting a right include the nature of the freedom, the importance of the purpose of the limitation, the nature and extent of the limitation, the need to ensure the enjoyment of rights by any individual does not limit the rights of other as well as whether there is a less restrictive way of achieving this purpose.

manner that is not provided for under Article 24 of the Constitution¹⁴ and which might infringe on the freedoms of expression and access to information.

It should be noted that not all fake news is bad, as indeed there are instances when fake news has promoted positive change.¹⁵ Negative fake news with no social value may endanger democracy by distorting the free choices of people and therefore needs to be curtailed. Consequently, countries around the world are grappling with finding modes of regulation that balances the need to enable social media to flourish on one part and the need to minimize the harm that fake news causes to democratic processes such as elections. Having suffered from the realities of fake news especially during the 2017 elections, it is necessary for Kenya to put in place suitable regulatory regime to curb the impact of negative fake news but taking into account the need to protect free speech.

The concern of this study is to find a framework which balances the harm of fake news on elections and upholding the fundamental freedoms of expression, free media and access to information.

1.1 Problem Statement

Although social media is now an indispensable mode of communication not just in Kenya but worldwide, fake news spread by it does sometimes have negative effects on democratic process such as it did on Kenya's general elections of 2013 and 2017. This has created the need to regulate social media to curb such negative impact on elections. However, some types of regulation can impact negatively on the fundamental freedoms of expression, free media and access to information. The study seeks to establish the adequacy or lack thereof of Kenya's existing social media regulatory framework in curbing the effect of fake news to on elections while at the same time protecting the fundamental freedoms of free speech, free media and access to information.

¹⁴ Patrick Mutahi and Brian Kimari, n. 4 p 6.

¹⁵ Ibid.

1.2 Justification

This study is justified by the following grounds;

1. Kenya has been experiencing the negative effects of fake news on elections since 2007 and has since been grappling with regulation mechanisms to curb this menace. There is however, few academic and intellectual studies that have been carried out on this subject. Existing literature has tended to focus on the historical aspects of social media phenomenon in Kenya without focusing on the problem of negative fake news on elections and the suitability of regulatory framework. There is therefore a paucity of literature on this subject, which this study seeks to fill.
2. Since 2007, Kenya has been grappling with the question of how to regulate social media in order to curb the impact of fake news on elections and in the process, the country has resorted to laws that criminalize certain aspects of social media news. There is therefore need for well researched information on regulatory mechanisms to assist legal and policy reforms in this area. This study seeks to make recommendations that can be used to reform laws and policy to ensure a balance between freedom of expression, free media and access to information as well as curb the negative impacts of fake news on the democratic process of elections.
3. Social media has become an important mode of communication not just in Kenya but around the world and there is need to contribute to knowledge on the subject. This study seeks to contribute to knowledge on the subject of social media and regulation in Kenya.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 Main Objective

The main objective of this study is to examine the adequacy of Kenya's social media regulatory framework and its ability to protect fundamental freedoms, curb harmful fake news as well as promote a flourishing social media space.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. To examine the theoretical and conceptual underpinnings of social media phenomenon and its role in democratic processes
2. To examine both the international and national legal framework for protection of fundamental freedoms and the adequacy of Kenya's regulatory framework to curb negative fake news and protect freedom of expression.
3. To make recommendations from experiences of other jurisdictions on the nature of the regulatory framework that curbs harmful fake news, protection of fundamental freedoms and promotion of free social media.

1.4 Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions: -

1. What are the theoretical and conceptual underpinnings of the social media phenomenon and its role in democratic processes?
2. Is Kenya's regulatory framework for social media adequate to balance the freedoms of expression, free media and access to information and to curb the menace of fake news on the electoral processes?
3. What recommendations can be made from other jurisdictions on a regulatory framework that can curb harmful fake news, protect fundamental freedoms and promote free social media.

1.5 Hypotheses

The hypothesis of this study is that Kenya does not have an adequate regulatory framework for curbing harmful social media content such as fake news, protect freedoms of expression, access to information and free media and promotion of free and vibrant social media.

1.6 Theoretical Framework or Conceptual Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is the principle of proportionality as propounded by Kai Moller. Proportionality is a doctrinal tool for the resolution of conflicts between a right and a competing right or interest, at the core of which is the balancing stage which requires the right to be balanced against the competing right or interest.¹⁶ Moller posits that proportionality is a test to determine whether an interference with a *prima facie* right is justified.¹⁷ One of the most common tests used to determine whether a limitation on the freedom of expression, which is central to this thesis, is justified is the ‘proportionality test’.¹⁸ A typical proportionality test assesses whether a limitation on a right can be ‘justified by reference to gains on some other interest or value’. Justification involves providing good reasons for an action, omission, or belief. Most theorists of proportionality take proportionality to imply that, among others, the law must not impose a disproportionate burden on the right-holder.¹⁹

Given the special value is attached to the freedom of expression, a reason must be of a particular kind when deployed to limit the freedom of expression.²⁰ According to Raz, a reason is ‘a consideration in favour of doing, believing, or feeling something’.²¹ Most jurisdictions in Europe, and treaty bodies such as the United Nations Human Rights Committee, apply the proportionality test when evaluating the permissibility of limitations.²² The test usually contains four limbs. First, the state must pursue an aim that serves a ‘compelling’ or ‘legitimate’ interest when limiting the right.²³ This limb contains a normative requirement, as certain interests that are ‘illegitimate’ would not be permissible at the outset. Second, there must be a rational nexus between the specific measure used to limit the right and the legitimate interest. This limb is sometime referred to as the ‘suitability test’.²⁴ Third, this measure must be necessary to advancing, or preventing setbacks to,

¹⁶ Ki Moller. Proportionality: Challenging the critics. *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, Volume 10, Issue 3, July 2012, Pages 709–731, <https://doi.org/10.1093/icon/mos024>

¹⁷ Ibid

¹⁸ Gehan Gunatilleke. Justifying Limitations on the Freedom of Expression. *Human Rights Review* (2021) 22:91–108 p 91

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Ibid p 95.

²¹ Raz J (1986) *The Morality of Freedom*. Clarendon Press, Oxford. Ibid

²² Ibid

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Ibid

that legitimate interest. This limb is naturally termed the necessity test. Finally, the measure must be, in the ‘strict sense’, proportionate, that is, it must involve a net gain, when the reduction in the enjoyment of the right is weighed against the level to which the interest is advanced.²⁵

The principle of proportionality plays a crucial role in the protection of fundamental rights. In European law, for instance, the concept of proportionality ‘implies a means-ends relationship between the aims pursued by a specific action of the government and the means employed to achieve this end’.²⁶ Moller states that reaching the balancing stage, the question is whether the interference with the right is justified in light of the gain in the protection for the competing right or interest. To this end, the two values have to be “balanced” against each other.²⁷

Experience has shown that dilemmas arise whenever a hallowed right such as freedom of expression encounters revolutionary technological innovation, which digitization implies.²⁸ The balance between freedom of expression and distortion of democracy becomes particularly problematic. The principle of proportionality will help this study to analyse the conflicting interests of curbing negative fake news on elections and the protection of the fundamental freedoms of expression, free media and access to information and to what extent the freedoms can be limited by such regulation.

1.7 Literature Review

Nyabola’s “*Digital Democracy, Analogue politics/How the Internet Era is Transforming Politics in Kenya*” offers a brilliant insight into the impact of technology on politics in Kenya and beyond.²⁹ The book opens up new ways of understanding the current online era. The book notes that social platforms are not neutral spaces but rather commercial platforms that reflect the developer’s

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Thomas Cottier, Roberto Echandi, Rafael Leal-Arcas, Rachel Liechti, Tetyana Payosova, Charlotte Sieber-Gasser. The Principle of Proportionality in International Law. NCCR TRADE WORKING PAPERS, Working Paper No 2012/38| December 2012 https://www.wti.org/media/filer_public/9f/1b/9f1bd3cf-dafd-4e14-b07d-8934a0c66b8f/proportionality_final_29102012_with_ncer_coversheet.pdf P 2.

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ (cf. Ellul 1964, Winston 1998, Hirschfeldt 2016, von Sydow 2016).

²⁹ Nanjala Nyabola. *Digital Democracy, Analogue politics/How the Internet Era is Transforming Politics in Kenya*. Zedbooks. CPI Group (UK) Ltd, Croydon P 80.

interest in making profit, allowing individuals and corporations to exert unprecedented agenda setting a preference-shaping power over the electorate. It notes that while this impact in Kenya is currently moderated by the relatively small population of voters using the platforms in a thin way, that number is growing rapidly by the day given developments in both technology and in the media.³⁰ This literature is useful in giving general insights into the phenomenon of fake news in Kenya's general elections. However, it does not address the issue of legal regulation of the phenomenon.

Patrick Mutahi and Brian Kimari in their work titled "*The Impact of Social Media and Digital Technology on Electoral Violence in Kenya*" give a history of how social media and fake news have grown in Kenya, tracing the phenomenon since the 2007 election. They note that electoral violence has become synonymous with Kenya's elections.³¹ This acquired deadly proportions during the 2007 election. However, it was also during this time that social media and digital technology were first used for political reasons, including campaigning and polling.³² The two locate their thesis within the context of electoral violence. They do not study social media and fake news as an area of legal concern in Kenya.

In his seminal treatise titled "*The Right to be Wrong: Examining the (Im) possibilities of Regulating Fake News while Preserving the Freedom of Expression in Kenya*" Abdulmalik Sugow seeks to find out if indeed, it is possible to regulate fake news while preserving the freedom of expression in Kenya. Further, the article delves into some of the effects the proliferation of fake news has had on the democratic process in Kenya, thereby requiring regulation.³³ Sugow writes that with the proliferation of peer-to-peer networks as a source of information, concerns on the accuracy of information shared have been raised, necessitating attempts by governments to regulate fake news. Kenya's Computer Misuse and Cybercrimes Act, for instance, criminalizes the intentional dissemination of false or misleading data. However, such regulation has resulted in a different set

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ Patrick Mutahi and Brian Kimari. *The Impact of Social Media and Digital Technology on Electoral Violence in Kenya*. Institute of Development Studies 2017 ISSN: 2040-0209 ISBN: 978-1-78118-381-6. IDS-CHRIPS-Working-Paper.pdf

³² Ibid

³³ Abdulmalik Sugow. *The Right to be Wrong: Examining the (Im) possibilities of Regulating Fake News while Preserving the Freedom of Expression in Kenya*. *Strathmore Law Review*, June 2019.

of concerns, particularly its potential to bring about the undue limitation on the freedom of expression.³⁴

Fernando Nuñez, in his work “*Disinformation Legislation and Freedom of Expression*” examines how the rise of disinformation on social media has prompted governments around the world to enact legislation that may affect every person’s right to freedom of opinion and expression.³⁵ He specifically seeks to explore the rise of disinformation and the legal framework that applies and to highlight some of the recent proposals to combat disinformation on social media. Tompros, Crudo, Pfeiffer and Boghossian in “*The Constitutionality of Criminalizing False Speech Made on Social Networking Sites in A Post-Alvarez, Social Media-obsessed World*”³⁶ write that with the advent of social media and modern digital communication there is a great opportunity for individuals to perpetuate mischief that can result in falsehoods. They note that the fake news epidemic that recently dominated the headlines provides an obvious example of such falsehoods, but there are many others. Hyperbole, embellishment, practical jokes, rumours, catfishing, and even malicious lies and threats are not uncommon on social media.³⁷

Whereas the studies under review are relevant and useful for the present study, the literature does not address the problem of adequacy of Kenya’s regulatory framework and how it balances between curbing negative fake news on elections and the protection of the fundamental freedoms of expression, free media and access to information hence the gap that ne this study seeks to fill.

1.8 Methodology

This study was by way of qualitative analysis through a desk review. It used both doctrinal and comparative methods. It drew on extensive literature by scholars and policymakers on the issue of laws for social media regulation. It specifically used secondary data collection technique which entailed going through the relevant books, articles, journals, conference papers, reports and

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ Fernando Nuñez. *Disinformation Legislation and Freedom of Expression*. UC IRVINE LAW REVIEW [Vol. 10:783

³⁶ Louis W. Tompros, Richard A. Crudo, Alexis Pfeiffer, Rahel . “THE CONSTITUTIONALITY OF CRIMINALIZING FALSE SPEECH MADE ON SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES IN A POST-ALVAREZ, SOCIAL MEDIA-OBSSESSED WORLD”. *Harvard Journal of Law & Technology* [Vol. 31. Number 1 Fall 2017.

³⁷ Ibid p 67.

information from the internet on the media regulation by the state. It also studied literature in other jurisdictions on how they have dealt with the issue of balancing the state interest to regulate social media and the interests of social media users and their rights and fundamental freedoms. It thus sampled best practice from other chosen jurisdictions.

1.9 Limitations

The study has relied on reports and other information as its study base and did not go into the field to interact with the social media users to understand the extent that government regulation of social media affects them and how far the harm fake news has on elections. Further, the field of social media keeps evolving each day and there could be new aspects that the study may not have captured, which is relevant.

1.10 Chapter breakdown

This study is divided into four chapters.

Chapter one gives the background to the study, the problem statement, justification of the study, the research objectives and the hypotheses as well as the research questions. It articulates the theoretical framework, literature review, methodology, limitations of the study as well as the chapter breakdown.

Chapter two examines the theoretical and conceptual underpinnings of social media regulation. It specifically discusses the concepts of social media and fake news. It further examines the related concepts of misinformation and disinformation. Examines the concept of and relationship between Democracy and Social Media.

Chapter three examines the legal framework for regulation of social media in Kenya. It discusses three important regulatory bodies, namely, the Media Council of Kenya, the Communication Authority of Kenya and Film Classification Board) and the Communications Authority of Kenya through KICA and their role in regulating media in Kenya. It also examines some important laws

currently used for regulating media, noting their inadequacies. It then explores best practice in social media regulation from chosen jurisdictions.

Chapter four gives a conclusion and makes recommendations for a more adequate regulatory framework for social media in view of the freedom of expression.

CHAPTER TWO

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL UNDERPINNINGS OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND FAKE NEWS

2.0 Introduction

Sociologist Fred Riggs rightly states that the crucial importance of concepts for social studies needs no emphasis and that the need to identify concepts, explicit and contextual is essential.³⁸ This study is underpinned by multiple and complex concepts which include, inter alia, social media and fake news, information and disinformation. It is also steeped in the theory of democracy. These concepts and theories are also rooted in a rich and equally complex history whose understanding sheds light on their significance and use. This chapter discusses the conceptual and theoretical underpinnings of social media, fake news and related concepts of information and disinformation. It and their nexus with democracy. The chapter further examines the theories of fundamental freedoms and their use in democratic processes.

2.1 Social Media

Social media is the term often used to refer to new forms of media that involve interactive participation. Often the development of media is divided into two different ages, the broadcast age and the interactive age. In the broadcast age, media were almost exclusively centralized where one entity—such as a radio or television station, newspaper company, or a movie production studio—distributed messages to many people. Feedback to media outlets was often indirect, delayed, and impersonal.³⁹ Mediated communication between individuals typically happened on a much smaller level, usually via personal letters, telephone calls, or sometimes on a slightly larger scale through means such as photocopied family newsletters. With the rise of digital and mobile technologies, interaction on a large scale became easier for individuals than ever before; and as such, a new

³⁸ Fred Riggs. The Importance of Concepts: Some Considerations on How They Might be Designated Less Ambiguously. *The American Sociologist*, 1979, Vol. 14, 172-185 p 172.

³⁹ Jimmie Manning (2014). Definition and Classes of Social Media, (Kerric Harvey, ed). In book: *Encyclopedia of Social Media and Politics* (pp.1158-1162) Sage Publications

media age was born where interactivity was placed at the center of new media functions.⁴⁰ One individual could now speak to many, and instant feedback was a possibility. Where citizens and consumers used to have limited and somewhat muted voices, now they could share their opinions with many.⁴¹ The low cost and accessibility of new technology also allowed more options for media consumption than ever before – and so instead of only a few news outlets, individuals now have the ability to seek information from several sources and to dialogue with others via message forums about the information posted. At the core of this ongoing revolution is social media.⁴²

On the academic side, a considerable body of knowledge has addressed the definition, formation and evolution of social media, often using slightly different terminology to capture the nuances within a diverse digital media ecosystem. They state that the use of the term “social media” emphasizes the ability of users to participate and contribute to content creation, social media have enabled the emergence of a new participatory digital sphere based on a many-to-many communication where users can dialogically interact and collaborate to the creation of content shaping the flow of communication.⁴³ McCay-Peet and Quan-Haase offer this definition:

Social media are web-based services that allow individuals, communities, and organizations to collaborate, connect, interact, and build community by enabling them to create, co-create, modifies, share, and engage with user-generated content that is easily accessible.⁴⁴

While most definitions focus on the functionality of social media, Miller et al depart from that approach and state: that “social media should not be seen primarily as the platforms upon which people post, but rather as the contents that are posted on these platforms.⁴⁵ An important distinction

⁴⁰ Ibid

⁴¹ Ibid

⁴² Ibid

⁴³ Francesca Bria. Social Media and their Impact on Organisations: building Firm Celebrity and Organisational Legitimacy through Social Media. PhD in Innovation and Entrepreneurship. Imperial College London Imperial College Business School

⁴⁴ McCay-Peet and Quan-Haase (2017: 17) MCCAY-PEET, L. & A. QUAN-HAASE 2017. What is Social Media and What Questions Can Social Media Research Help Us Answer? In The SAGE Handbook of Social Media Research Methods (eds) L. Sloan & A. Quan-Haase. ProQuest Ebook Central.

⁴⁵ (Miller et al. 2016: 61)

MILLER, D., E. COSTA, N. HAYNES, ET AL. 2016. How the World Changed Social Media. London: UCL Press

needs to be mentioned also – social network sites (SNS) are not the same as social media, but useful to consider in this context also.

A social network site is a *networked communication platform* in which participants 1) have uniquely identifiable profiles that consist of user-supplied content, content provided by other users, and/or system level data; 2) can *publicly articulate connections* that can be viewed and traversed by others; and 3) can consume, produce, and/or interact with *streams of user-generated content* provided by their connections on the site.⁴⁶

2.2 Fake News

The Cambridge Dictionary defines fake news as stories that appear to be news, spread on the internet or using other media, usually created to influence political views or as a joke.⁴⁷ Fake news has come to be widely regarded as false and misleading content that purports to be true, and is intentionally disseminated on traditional forms of media or on social media.⁴⁸ There is the recognition that the medium of the internet (and social media, in particular) has been especially conducive to the creation and proliferation of fake news.⁴⁹ Thus, ‘fake news’ is sometimes explicitly defined as “the online publication” of false statements of fact⁵⁰ or it is noted that a “core feature of contemporary fake news is that it is widely circulated online”.⁵¹ It should also be noted that fake news is, a form of news.⁵²

Although now there is a seemingly simple dictionary definition of “fake news” as “false stories that appear to be news, spread on the Internet or using other media, usually created to influence political views or as a joke”, determining what is and what is not false is rather complex.⁵³ There

⁴⁶MILLER, D., E. COSTA, N. HAYNES, ET AL. 2016. How the World Changed Social Media. London: UCL Press (2013: 158;

⁴⁷ See Cambridge Dictionary.

⁴⁸ Allcott H and Gentzkow M, ‘Social Media and Fake News in the 2016 Election,’ 31(2) Journal of Economic Perspectives, 2017 p 213.

⁴⁹ Ibid

⁵⁰ David O. and Joshua R. Wueller. 2017. Fake news: a legal perspective. Journal of Internet Law 20(10): 5-13, , p. 6). In Axel Gelfert. Fake News: A Definition journal Informal Logic , Volume 38, Issue 1, 2018, p. 84–117.

⁵¹ Bakir, Vian and Andrew McStay. 2017. Fake news and the economy of emotions: problems, causes, solutions. Digital Journalism (DOI: 10.1080/21670811.2017.1345645, p p. 1).

⁵² Axel Gelfert. Fake News: A Definition journal Informal Logic , Volume 38, Issue 1, 2018, p. 84–117.

p 103

⁵³ Ibid

is considerable disagreement when it comes to determining which content should be considered “fake news” and which should be excluded. Gelfert argues that the term fake news should be reserved for cases of deliberate presentation of (typically) false or misleading claims as news, where these are misleading by design. And by the phrase ‘by design’ Gelfert refers to systemic features of the design of the sources and channels by which fake news propagates and, thereby, manipulates the audience’s cognitive processes.⁵⁴

Literature about fake news stresses notions of selective exposure and attention, arguing that fake news stories are disseminated mainly in ideological echo chambers or cyber-ghettos.⁵⁵ The end result is that social media users with ideologically clear allegiances will be more likely to see ideologically-congruent fake news stories on their feeds. On the demand side, these users are furthermore going to be more likely to select and read these stories.⁵⁶ Also congruent with the argument about online echo chambers, findings show that fact-checking information travels selectively online.⁵⁷ What makes fake news an extremely hard problem to solve is the difficulty in identifying, tracking and controlling unreliable content.⁵⁸

As discussed above, fake news is not itself a new phenomenon. Yet, when combined with online social media that enable the targeted, audience-specific manipulation of cognitive biases and heuristics, it forms a potent—and, as the events of 2016 show, politically explosive—mix.⁵⁹ As opposed to disinformation by political actors, a main characteristic of the fake news is that the original producers of the information are harder to trace given that they purposively hide their true identity when presenting the information as originating from a legitimate news outlet. The phenomenon is not restricted to the U.S.: similar phenomena can be found across the world,

⁵⁴ Ibid

⁵⁵ Lewandowsky, S., Ecker, U. K. H., Seifert, C. M., Schwarz, N., & Cook, J. (2012). Misinformation and its correction: Continued influence and successful debiasing. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 13(3), 106–131.

⁵⁶ Bakshy, E., Messing, S., & Adamic, L. A. (2015). Exposure to ideologically diverse news and opinion on Facebook. *Science*, 348(6239), 1130–1132.

⁵⁷ Hameleers, M., & van der Meer, T. G. L. A. (2019). Misinformation and Polarization in a high-choice media environment: How effective are political fact-checkers? *Communication Research*, Article 0093650218819671. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093650218819671>

⁵⁸ Ibid

⁵⁹ Ibid p 113

ranging from Latin America and Africa.⁶⁰ Fake news and misinformation is a major problem of the modern, connected world. The spread of fake news on the Internet is a cause of great concern for all members of society, including the government, policymakers, organizations, businesses and citizens. Fake news is specifically designed to plant a seed of mistrust and exacerbate the existing social and cultural dynamics by misusing political, regional and religious undercurrents.⁶¹ Shu et al. argue that fake news has an adverse impact on individuals and society as it deliberately persuades consumers to accept false beliefs that are shared to forward specific agendas.⁶²

This study used fake news as posited by Gelfert; that it is content that is not only factually incorrect, but also framed as an accurate assertion, the key aspect being a deliberate and calculated misleading nature of the content.

2.3 Misinformation

Although we can easily understand the general concept of misinformation, in academic discussion, clarifying the definition of misinformation is complex. Misinformation has many similar concepts or sub-concepts, such as disinformation, rumours, and fake news.⁶³ By definition, misinformation is false or inaccurate information that is deliberately created and is intentionally or unintentionally propagated. This distinction suggests that “intentionality” is the core factor to differentiate between misinformation and disinformation. However, variances of the definition remain amongst different researchers and disciplines.⁶⁴ For instance, some scholars attribute fake news and conspiracy theories to the range of misinformation. Under many situations, fake news and

⁶⁰ Tedeneke, A. (2018). Fake news poses a threat to democracies across Latin America and worldwide. <https://www.weforum.org/press/2018/03/fake-news-poses-a-threat-to-democracies-across-latin-america-and-worldwide/>

⁶¹ Shu, K., Sliva, A., Wang, S., Tang, J., Liu, H., 2017. Fake news detection on social media. ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newslett. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3137597.3137600>.

⁶²Ibid.

⁶³ Van der Meer TA, Jin Y. Seeking formula for misinformation treatment in public health crises: the effects of corrective information type and source. *Health Commun.* 2020;35(5):560–575. doi:10.1080/10410236.2019.1573295

⁶⁴ Miroslav T, Mikelic N. Information science: science about information misinformation and disinformation. Available from: <http://proceedings.informingscience.org/IS2003Proceedings/index.html>.

conspiracy theories are always based on intention, because they either misinform people or merely attract clicks for the purpose of converting them into advertising money.⁶⁵

Some misinformation is unintentional to deceive its recipients. Regular and benign users may contribute to the propagation merely due to their trust of information sources, such as their friends, family, colleagues or influential users in the social network. Instead of wanting to deceive, they usually try to inform their social network friends of a certain issue or situation. An example is the widespread misinformation about Ebola.⁶⁶ Misinformation always spreads in a “florid” environment filled by functional illiteracy, information overload, and confirmation bias.⁶⁷

2.4 Disinformation

Higgins defines disinformation as the intentional and purposive spread of misleading information.⁶⁸ The term ‘disinformation’, more so than the relatively recent expression ‘fake news’, has by now received considerable attention from epistemologists and has been subjected to extensive conceptual analysis. Like ‘fake news’, ‘disinformation’ derives from a prior, philosophically more “respectable” notion: the notion of information, which in recent years has led to a burgeoning literature in the philosophy of information.⁶⁹ While disinformation has circulated through media since the early days of mass communication, scholars and pundits have argued that recent years mark ‘the rise of the misinformation society⁷⁰’ and the era of ‘alternative facts’ and ‘post truth’.⁷¹ As Higgins explains, the term ‘post-truth’ describes not only an increase in the frequency of lies in the public sphere, but refers to a world in which truth is no longer an expectation.⁷²

⁶⁵ Shin J, Jian L, Driscoll K, et al. Political rumoring on twitter during the 2012 us presidential election: rumor diffusion and correction. *New Media Soc.* 2016;19(8):1214–1235. doi:10.1177/1461444816634054

⁶⁶ J. Bollen, H. Mao, and A. Pepe. Determining the public mood state by analysis of microblogging posts. In ALIFE, pages 667–668, 2010.

⁶⁷ Ibid

⁶⁸ Higgins, K. (2016). Post-truth: A guide for the perplexed. *Nature News*, 540(7631), 9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/540009a>, p. 9)

⁶⁹ Floridi, Luciano. 2011. The philosophy of information. Oxford. Oxford University Press. In Gerfert p 103

⁷⁰ Pickard, V. (2016). Media failures in the age of Trump. *The Political Economy of Communication*, 4(2). <http://polecom.org/index.php/polecom/article/viewFile/74/264>

⁷¹ Benkler, Y., Faris, R., & Roberts, H. (2018). *Network propaganda: Manipulation, disinformation, and radicalization in American politics*. Oxford University Press, p. 119

⁷² Higgins (2016, p. 9)

The rise in use of disinformation has increased exponentially. While political actors have probably always exaggerated, misled or at times even lied, it seems both the frequency of lies and their centrality in the strategy of some political actors have increased in recent years. Politicians' opportunities to disseminate disinformation directly to the public, bypassing the media's gatekeeping and their editorial scrutiny, have increased with the rise of social media and the possibilities they afford and with a weakening of what Graves and Wells call 'factual accountability'.⁷³

Another cause of disinformation lies with the rise of 'the fake news genre' referring to the intentional spread of false information, masked as traditional news, to advance political goals or generate ad revenues.⁷⁴

2.5 Democracy and Social Media

During the twentieth century many scholars have tried to explain democracy in broad and narrow meanings. The concept of democracy has been constantly evolving making previous research obsolete and outdated consequently creating the need and space for further research and explanation.⁷⁵ As Diamond argues, there is a powerful association between democracy and liberty which means that countries that hold free elections are overwhelmingly more liberal than those that do not.⁷⁶ Assuming this as a main feature of the modern democracies one can separate out several key features typical for democracy. Starting with minimalist definition which is often called electoral democracy, it implies a system for arriving at political decisions in which individuals acquire the power to decide by means of a competitive struggle for the people's vote.⁷⁷ Competitive elections were also defined as an essence of democracy earlier by Robert Dahl: according to whom democracy implies holding elections in which the opposition has some chance

⁷³ Graves, L., & Wells, C. (2019). From information availability to factual accountability. In J. Katz & K. Mays (Eds.), *Journalism and truth in an age of social media* (pp. 39–57). Oxford University Press. p. 42

⁷⁴ Bennett, W. L., & Livingston, S. (2018). The disinformation order: Disruptive communication and the decline of democratic institutions. *European Journal of Communication*, 33(2), 122–139.

⁷⁵ Sergiy Prokhorov. Social Media and Democracy: Facebook as a Tool for the Establishment of Democracy in Egypt. Malmö University Master Thesis Master Thesis School of Arts and Communication Spring 2012, p 19.

⁷⁶ Ibid

⁷⁷ Ibid p 20

of winning and taking office.⁷⁸ Besides opposition and participation as necessary conditions for democracy, Dahl also added civil liberty which implied freedom to speak and publish dissenting views, freedom to form and join organizations and alternative sources of information.⁷⁹

The rise of the Internet has led to burgeoning literature on the probable effects of emerging information and communication technologies (ICTs) on democratic processes. The breadth of the debate is impressive, largely due to the complexity of democratic governance and the historic implications of the information age.⁸⁰ The Internet expands one's capability of information sharing, hence having a positive effect on their freedom of speech, which is one of the fundamental principles of democracy.⁸¹ Thus, Internet technology has created political opportunities, including new potentials for direct democracy and other bottom-up, self-organizing political forms.⁸²

Internet platforms have vastly increased the ability of voters to access and interact with information about political parties and candidates. Political parties, especially small ones are more able to than ever before to get their message out to larger audiences, especially spending less by using free blogs, video sharing platforms and social media.⁸³ But increasingly clear from recent elections, the same openness can pose serious challenges to the right of citizens to freely choose elected representatives. The use of targeted political advertising and coordinated inauthentic behaviour to disseminate misinformation have led to fears over the integrity of elections. Many of the traditional safeguards to ensure the fairness of elections are difficult to apply online.⁸⁴

A broad spectrum of public opinion has long portrayed the Internet as a harbinger of liberal-democratic ethos-renewal. This is true. However, recent empirical evidence, points to opposite, ethos-reversing effects.⁸⁵ The phenomenon of fake news and its impact on election as has

⁷⁸ Ibid

⁷⁹ Ibid

⁸⁰ Manuel Castells. Democracy in the age of the Internet. https://lull.cat/IMAGES_175/transfer06-not01.pdf

⁸¹ Ibid

⁸² Ibid

⁸³ <https://www.article19.org/elections-freedom-of-expression/>

⁸⁴ Ibid

⁸⁵ M Hensmans. Exploring the dark and bright sides of Internet democracy: Ethos-reversing and ethos-renewing digital transformation. Technological Forecasting and Social Change Volume 168, July 2021, 120777

happened in Kenyan elections since 2007, is one such effect of reversing the gains of social media on democracy.

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter has examined some important concepts and theories that underpin the phenomena of social media and fake news. The chapter has specifically discussed fake news and related concepts of misinformation and disinformation in the dynamic social media environment. What is deducible from this comparison is that these are closely related concepts which are sometimes used interchangeably, but whose distinction is important. Most importantly, however, is that understanding the various ways that false information is shared, and the motives and appeal behind it, is important in avoiding and combating it. The chapter has further discussed the nexus between democracy, elections and social media, establishing that there is a strong nexus among the three, but also noted that there is a downside to internet and social media use to the democracy. It has shown that fake news is a threat to democratic processes, an occurrence that has taken root in recent years.

CHAPTER THREE

LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR REGULATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN KENYA

3.0 Introduction

The exponential growth of internet access and use coupled with the ever-increasing uptake of digital technologies has presented new and unique challenges to elective processes globally. As discussed in chapter one of this study, the effects of fake news purveyed through social media on the 2007, 2013 and 2017 elections demonstrate that there is a need for social media regulation to tame negative fake news. The study has also established that freedom of expression and free media is necessary for the exchange of information and all these are fundamental in a democracy such as Kenya. As noted in chapter one, the Constitution of Kenya 2010 outlines certain fundamental rights in Chapter Four on the Bill of Rights. The Constitution in Section 33- Freedom of Expression gives citizens the right to entertain and impart information without interference from any quarter including the state or any of its agencies. Section 34- Freedom of the press and Section 35- Access to Information all together guarantee Kenyan citizens and the press enjoyment of fundamental rights pertaining to communication.⁸⁶

Whereas there is a need to regulate social media in the wake of the harm caused to the election process, there is a need for proportionality in order to strike a balance between limiting social media to curb negative fake news and promotion of freedom of media. As rightly posited by McQuail, regulation of media content should be based on accountability and responsibility.⁸⁷ He says that regulation should be based on accountability which has to meet certain general aims: 1. Accountability should protect and promote media freedom. 2. It should prevent or limit harm which the media might cause. 3. Accountability should promote positive benefits from media to society. He further argues that freedom is not well served by coercive forms of control or by

⁸⁶ Constitution of Kenya, 2010.

⁸⁷ McQuail. (2005). Mass Communication Theory. Fifth Edition. In Jasper Otieno. Regulation of Media Content in Kenya: In Search of a Paradigm in the Era of Convergence. Saudi J. Humanities Soc. Sci.; Vol-2, Iss-7(Jul, 2017):556-566 p 556.

making the media more liable for consequences that are considered harmful.⁸⁸ International human rights instruments as discussed in chapter two also put limitations to State regulation of freedom of expression, free media and access to information. The UDHR at Article 29 qualifies this right as follows: ...determined by law solely for the purpose of securing due recognition and respect for the rights and freedom of others and of meeting the just requirements of morality, public order and general welfare in a democratic society.⁸⁹ Article 24 of the Constitution of Kenya also spells out the parameters within which these freedoms can be limited.

Unlike traditional media, there is a glaring absence of fact-checking and content filtration on social media platforms, raising concerns around their level of involvement in democracies.⁹⁰ Hence, the very characteristics that make social media particularly effective in fostering political engagement are the ones that create opportunities for misuse. It is therefore necessary to discuss social media regulation in Kenya where ICT laws and policies are currently being enacted at a steadily increasing rate. This chapter examines the institutional and legal framework for the regulation of media in Kenya and how adequate they are for the social media phenomenon. It will compare the statutory regulation which is the preferred mode of media regulation in Kenya as well as self-regulation in order to find a suitable mode of regulation that balances public good as well as promote fundamental freedoms discussed above.

3.1 Institutional and Legal Regulatory Framework in Kenya.

The development of the media can be traced way back to the colonial era. Many people believe that the first newspaper in Kenya was the East Africa Standard in 1901, while according to history, the press was started by Rev Albert Stegal of the Church Missionary Society when it published the Taveta Chronicle in 1895.⁹¹ Media regulation in Kenya is traced to the colonial period, it evolved through in the post-colonial era and it builds momentum in the 21st century. After the 2002 general election when the Kenya African National Union (KANU) was ousted from power, the era of

⁸⁸ Jasper Otieno. Regulation of Media Content in Kenya: In Search of a Paradigm in the Era of Convergence. Saudi J. Humanities Soc. Sci.; Vol-2, Iss-7(Jul, 2017):556-566 p 564.

⁸⁹ Ibid

⁹⁰ Isaac Rutenberg and Abdulmalik Sugow. Regulation of the Social Media in Electoral Democracies: A Case of Kenya. SLJ 7 (1) p 301.

⁹¹ Oriare, P., Orlale, R., Ugangu (2009), The Media we want: The Kenya Media Vulnerabilities Study. Friedrich Ebert Stiftung: Nairobi

NARC government saw various liberating legislative and institutional reforms for the media that saw an upsurge in the number of broadcast stations.⁹²

3.1.1 Institutional Mechanisms

To promote responsible media behaviour, the Kenyan Parliament passed the Media Act, 2007, which established the Media Council of Kenya (a press council) to oversee ethical journalism and mediate in disputes between the media, the public and the government through self-regulation.⁹³ The functions of the Media Council of Kenya are meant to promote and protect the freedom and independence of the media. They include, among others, to mediate or arbitrate in disputes between the government and the media, between the public and the media and intra-media.⁹⁴ The Media Council Act, 2013 also established in Section 102, the Complaints Commission of the Media Council of Kenya. Its mandate is to mediate and adjudicate the disputes between the government and the media, and between the public and the media and intra media on ethical issues.⁹⁵

Until 1997 the Kenyan media was operated as a monopoly.⁹⁶ The proliferation of mass media, economic demands and pressure from donors, as well as civil society, forced the government in 1998 to review the laws governing the media with a view to liberalizing the airwaves, abolishing of restrictive media laws, and harmonization of Kenya Posts and Telecommunication Act and Kenya Broadcasting Acts.⁹⁷ In 1997, the first policy paper specific to telecommunication and postal sector liberalization was issued based on the Economic Recovery strategy for wealth creation (2002-2007). The policy guideline led to the transformation of the telecommunications and postal sector, the creation of the Kenya Communications Act (KCA, 1998) and the Postal Corporation Act (1998).

⁹² Jasper Otieno. Regulation of Media Content in Kenya: In Search of a Paradigm in the Era of Convergence. Saudi J. Humanities Soc. Sci.; Vol-2, Iss-7(Jul, 2017):556-566 p 556.

⁹³ JARED OBUYA. Self-regulation as a tool for ensuring media accountability: The Kenyan experience. PACIFIC JOURNALISM REVIEW 18 (2) 2012, p 131.

⁹⁴ Ibid

⁹⁵ Ibid

⁹⁶ Ibid

⁹⁷ Ibid

The Kenya Communication Act 1998 created the Communications Commission of Kenya (CCK) and gave it authority to regulate the information and communication sector.⁹⁸ The Kenya Communication and Information (Amendment) Act 2013 was enacted to address the need to give effect to Article 34 of the Constitution of Kenya which guarantees media freedom. Wanyama argues that everyone relies on the media for information, education, and entertainment among other needs. The media has a central to play in the freedom of information and expression. To contain powerful sources of information, entertainment and education, the government uses regulation to capture, limit or control the media. He further argues that most governments including Kenya government are likely to control media operations by all means, and that is only why the Kenya Information and Communication Act, 2013 was enacted.⁹⁹ Section 102 of Kenya Information and Communications (Amendment) Act, 2013 provides for the establishment of the Communications and Multimedia Appeals Tribunal of the Communications Authority of Kenya (CAK) whose mandate is to adjudicate and mediate in disputes between the government and the media, public and the media and intra media. ¹⁰⁰

Media stakeholders in Kenya had wanted to have self-regulation in the media industry. Three regulatory bodies (Media Council of Kenya, Communication Authority of Kenya and Film Classification Board) have been established through legislation to regulate media content and practice.¹⁰¹ The Communications Authority of Kenya through KICA is to facilitate the development of the information and communications sector (including broadcasting, multimedia, telecommunications and postal services) and electronic commerce. This also means that it has the mandate to regulate content on television, radio. Media Council of Kenya is also mandated to regulate journalism practice including monitoring the content that they publish and broadcast.¹⁰² The Communications Authority of Kenya (CAK) is the chief regulator for the communications sector in Kenya and is established by the Kenya Information and Communications Act of 1998 (later revised in 2009). One of the core functions of CAK is to license all systems and services in

⁹⁸ Otieno, N. (2014) The impact of Kenya's legal and institutional frameworks on media freedom (2014). Article 19 East African: Nairobi

⁹⁹ Ibid

¹⁰⁰ Ibid

¹⁰¹ Jasper Otieno. Regulation of Media Content in Kenya: In Search of a Paradigm in the Era of Convergence. Saudi J. Humanities Soc. Sci.; Vol-2, Iss-7(Jul, 2017):556-566 p 556.

¹⁰² Ibid p 563.

the communications industry, including licensing persons to administer a sub-domain in the country code top-level domain.¹⁰³

3.1.2 Legal Framework

There are several laws in Kenya that touch on the media and have been used to regulate traditional media. They comprise of 1. The Armed Forces Act, CAP 199; 2. The Books and Newspapers Act, CAP 111; 3. The Chief's Authority Act CAP 128; 4. The Copyright Act, CAP 130; 5. The Defamation Act, CAP 36; 6. The Films and Stage Plays Act, CAP 22; 7. The Official Secrets Act, CAP 187; 8. The Police Act, CAP 84; 9. The Preservation of Public Security Act, CAP 57; 10. The Public Order Act, CAP 56; 11. The Kenya Broadcasting Act, CAP 221; 12. The Kenya Information and Communications Act, 2013; and 13. The Media Act, 2013.

All these statutes can be used to address social media problems. These statutes have strong anti-media laws. Most of them undermine media freedom as they are largely retrospective, punitive and repressive. The statutes promote censorship and encourage self-censorship.¹⁰⁴ The Books and Newspapers Act requires that publishers and printers execute a bond of Ksh One million each. It also requires publishers to deposit two copies of each publication with the Attorney General. The vendors must also display the bond as proof of registration of the publications.¹⁰⁵ The Official Secrets Act prohibits the media from telling the truth. It is a clawback to freedom as it stops the media from performing their job freely and effectively. It hinders journalists from accessing information and discourages public officials from providing sensitive information while awarding huge penalties against journalists found in breach.¹⁰⁶

¹⁰³ William Oyange Auma. Copyright in the Digital Age: An Assessment of Kenya's Legal and Institutional Framework for the Protection and Enforcement of Copyright. A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements of Master of Laws (L.M) Degree, School of Law, University of Nairobi. June, 2017. P68

¹⁰⁴ Okore, Jackline. A Regulation of media comparative analysis of regulation of broadcasting services in Kenya. A project submitted in partial fulfillment of the academic requirement of Master's Degree at the Nairobi University School of Journalism and Mass Communication 11th November 2014, p 38.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid

Particularly the Penal Code and the Information and Communications Act, bar the dissemination of false information in different contexts.¹⁰⁷ These laws apply to traditional media regulation but are used for social media content regulation. This section examines the adequacy or otherwise of these laws for the regulation of social media content and fake news.

3.1.3.1 The Penal Code

This is a 1930 piece of legislation that has some draconian provisions. The Penal Code criminalizes what it calls “alarming publications.” It states that “[a]ny person who publishes any false statement, rumour or report which is likely to cause fear and alarm to the public or to disturb the public peace is guilty of a misdemeanour.” A person found to have committed this offense is, on conviction, subject to a custodial sentence not exceeding two years and/or a fine.¹⁰⁸ The Code further states that “[i]t shall be a defence to a charge under [the “alarming publications” clause] if the accused proves that, prior to publication, he took such measures to verify the accuracy of the statement, rumour or report as to lead him reasonably to believe that it was true.”¹⁰⁹

Until recently, the Code also criminalized defamation. Section 194 of the Code defined defamation. It stated that “Any person who, by print, writing, painting or effigy, or by any means otherwise than solely by gestures, spoken words or other sounds, unlawfully publishes any defamatory matter concerning another person, with intent to defame that other person, is guilty of the misdemeanour termed libel.”¹¹⁰ These provisions were used to punish persons charged with criminal defamation and this posed a threat to free speech. Fortunately, on February 6, 2017, the Constitutional and Human Rights Division of the High Court found unconstitutional Article 194 of the Penal Code, which relates to criminal defamation.¹¹¹ (Kenya Law website.) Two individuals, Jacqueline Okuta and Jackson Njeru, who were each on two separate occasions arraigned on criminal defamation charges for posting items on the Facebook page *Buyer Beware-Kenya*, brought the petition challenging the legality and continued enforcement of the provision.

¹⁰⁷ Library of Congress. Initiatives to Counter Fake News: Kenya

¹⁰⁸ Ibid

¹⁰⁹ Ibid

¹¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹¹ See *Jacqueline Okuta & another v Attorney General & 2 others* [2017] eKLR

The challenge relied on two provisions of the 2010 Kenyan Constitution: the freedom of expression clause and the limitation of rights and fundamental freedoms clause.¹¹²

3.1.3.2 Kenya Information and Communication Act

This is an Act of Parliament to provide for the establishment of the Communications Commission of Kenya, to facilitate the development of the information and communications sector (including broadcasting, multimedia, telecommunications and postal services) and electronic commerce, to provide for the transfer of the functions, powers, assets and liabilities of the Kenya Posts and Telecommunication Corporation to the Commission, the Telkom Kenya Limited and the Postal Corporation of Kenya, and for connected purposes. The Act at Section 29 criminalized the “improper use” of a telecommunication system, stating that anyone who, through a licensed telecommunication system, (a) sends a message or other matter that is grossly offensive or of an indecent, obscene or menacing character; or (b) sends a message that he knows to be false for the purpose of causing annoyance, inconvenience or needless anxiety to another person.¹¹³ commits an offence and shall be liable on conviction to a fine not exceeding fifty thousand shillings, or to imprisonment for a term not exceeding three months, or to both.¹¹⁴ In 2015, a number of social media users were arrested and charged under this section. In an ensuing court case challenging the constitutionality of this provision, the section was struck down by the High Court.¹¹⁵ In declaring this section of the law unconstitutional, Justice Mumbi Ngugi ruled that, as well as being overreaching and broad, the section was in contradiction of Article 33 of the Constitution of Kenya, which guarantees the right to freedom of expression, including the freedom to seek, receive, or impart information or ideas.¹¹⁶

¹¹² See The Constitution of Kenya (2010), sections 24 & 33.

¹¹³ Ibid S 16

¹¹⁴ Kenya Information and Communications Act No. 2 of 1998, § 29 (commencement of relevant sections, July 1, 1999), <http://www.kenyalaw.org/lex//actview.xql?actid=No. 2 of 1998>, archived at <https://perma.cc/W4EZRFT2>.

¹¹⁵ See *Geoffrey Andare v Attorney General & 2 others* [2016] Eklr.

¹¹⁶ Hanibal Goitom. The Law Library of Congress. Initiatives to Counter Fake News in Selected Countries.

[https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jenny-](https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jenny-Gesley/publication/345361074_Initiatives_to_Counter_Fake_News_in_Selected_Countries_Argentina_Brazil_Canada_China_Egypt_France)

[Gesley/publication/345361074_Initiatives_to_Counter_Fake_News_in_Selected_Countries_Argentina_Brazil_Canada_China_Egypt_France](https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jenny-Gesley/publication/345361074_Initiatives_to_Counter_Fake_News_in_Selected_Countries_Argentina_Brazil_Canada_China_Egypt_France).

3.1.3.3 The Computer Misuse and Cybercrimes Act, 2018

The most recent legislation relating to social media is the Computer Misuse and Cybercrimes Act, 2018.¹¹⁷ The Act provides for offences relating to computer systems; it enables timely and effective detection, prohibition, prevention, response, investigation and prosecution of computer and cybercrimes; it facilitates international co-operation in dealing with computer and cybercrime matters amongst other provisions. Its objective is to provide for offences relating to computer systems, enabling among other things, prompt detection and prosecution of computer and cybercrimes. The Act among other things criminalizes fake news as well as publication of false information.¹¹⁸ Sections 22 and 23 of the Act criminalize false publication and publication of false information. Violations to be penalized under the law include cyber-espionage, false publications, child pornography, computer-borne forgery, cyber-stalking and cyber-bullying among others, the statement said, without spelling out the penalties. Offenders convicted for sharing "false" or "fictitious" information and propagating hate speech will be liable to a fine of 5 million shillings (\$49,776.01) or sentenced to two years in jail, or both.¹¹⁹

Proponents of the law, including the legislators who pushed it through parliament, say the proliferation of social media has given rise to new crimes including online scams, which were not covered by previous laws., but critics of the law say it could be exploited to repress civil liberties.¹²⁰ Indeed, shortly after its enactment, the Bloggers Association of Kenya (BAKE) challenged its constitutional basis in the High Court on account of infringing on Article 33 of the Constitution of Kenya relating to freedom of speech.¹²¹ The petitioner's core contention was that truth was not a condition of free speech and that any law purporting to regulate the truth in a

¹¹⁷ In May 2018, President Uhuru Kenyatta signed into law the Computer Misuse and Cyber Crimes Act.

¹¹⁸ Peter Roudik. Initiatives to Counter Fake News in Selected Countries.

[https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jenny-](https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jenny-Gesley/publication/345361074_Initiatives_to_Counter_Fake_News_in_Selected_Countries_Argentina_Brazil_Canada_China_Egypt_Fr)

[Gesley/publication/345361074_Initiatives_to_Counter_Fake_News_in_Selected_Countries_Argentina_Brazil_Canada_China_Egypt_Fr](https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jenny-Gesley/publication/345361074_Initiatives_to_Counter_Fake_News_in_Selected_Countries_Argentina_Brazil_Canada_China_Egypt_Fr)

¹¹⁹ Ibid

¹²⁰ Ibid

¹²¹ High Court Petition 206 Bloggers Association of Kenya (BAKE) v Attorney General & 3 others; Article 19 East Africa & another (Interested Parties) [2020] eKLR

manner so vague as to use sweeping terms such as ‘false, misleading or fictitious’ would countenance a violation of the freedom of expression.¹²²

On 20th February 2020, Justice Makau gave the final judgment that upheld, in entirety, the constitutionality of the Act. The court held that the need to protect the wider public from dangers in the cyberspace outweighs the granting of the petition. They found that the provisions of the Act effectively protect public interest and that public interest needs to be held in the highest esteem. Critics have panned the law as another opportunity for the government to clampdown on freedom of expression. According to Olewe, “[t]here is a serious risk that, as has happened in the past with issues such as anti-terror legislation, governments manipulate a genuine issue in order to push repressive changes that are really designed to strengthen their own power.”¹²³

3.4 The Inadequacy of the Legal Framework

As stated in the preceding chapter, fake news is believed to have featured in the country’s 2017 general election. A lot of misleading information on different sides of the political divide was allegedly circulated. Even more recently, the Cabinet Secretary for Information, Communication and Technology, Joe Mucheru, remarked that there were 70 cases of inaccurate, misleading or sensational news reported to the Media Council of Kenya.¹²⁴ The 2018 Cybercrimes Act has been used in recent times to curb fake news.

In Section 22(1), the Cybercrimes Act provides that publication of false, misleading or fictitious data is an offence. It does so without providing for any definitions within its interpretation section. As discussed above in the *Geoffrey Andare v Attorney General & 2 Others* case, this was sufficient ground for Ngugi J, to declare Section 29 of the Kenya Information and Communication Act unconstitutional.¹²⁵ In paragraph 77 of the judgment, the judge questioned the use of ambiguous terms such as ‘grossly offensive’. It was further reasoned that such ambiguity may result in a varied

¹²² Ibid

¹²³ Dickens Olewe, Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania ‘Anti-Fake News Campaigns’, BBC NEWS (May 16, 2018), <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-44137769>, archived at <https://perma.cc/3HCB-LGDH>.

¹²⁴ Abdulmalik Sugow. N. 2 p 33

¹²⁵ *Geoffrey Andare v Attorney General & 2 others* (2016), eKLR. In Abdulmalik Sugow. *The Right to be Wrong: Examining the (Im) possibilities of Regulating Fake News while Preserving the Freedom of Expression in Kenya*. *Strathmore Law Review*, June 2019 p 33.

understanding of the legislation, making the judicial officer in question the determiner of what constitutes gross offensiveness.¹²⁶

The Cybercrimes law, as rightly argued by Laibuta, hardly meets the threshold of a penal provision that constitutionally provides for the limitation of fundamental rights and freedoms.¹²⁷ The above provision is currently being used to arrest and charge individuals who post or spread fake news and misinformation. Vague terminology in the law leaves room for the violation of digital rights as well as the misuse of the laws by government or individuals. In fact, there is already evidence for these impacts.¹²⁸ Because of such forms of regulation, it has been argued that Kenya, constantly hovering at the margins of authoritarianism, has repeatedly tried to pass laws to curb political organization on social media, hinting at the increasing political potency of these spaces.¹²⁹

The inadequacy of this law is that it is vague on various aspects, one, how does one prove motive to create panic or chaos or violence? Two, how does one measure panic? Is it panic by one person or more than one person? Freedom of expression and free press exist on the premise that a democratic society ought to allow a free market of ideas. This free market enables society to sift through diverse views, opinions and facts; in the long run, ideally, the ‘truth’ is meant to triumph in such an environment.¹³⁰ The lack of a concrete definition of hate speech also adds to the inadequacy of the law for this issue. Benesch highlights this, pointing out that it is difficult ‘to draw the line between speech, which should be sanctioned, and speech that must be tolerated in the name of freedom of expression, no matter how ugly it may be’.¹³¹ The implications of the punitive and disjointed regulatory framework on the market place of ideas in Kenya cannot, therefore, be underestimated. The complexity of definitions aside, it can also be argued from this, as does this study, that laws are not enough to regulate social media. There is a need for polished

¹²⁶ Abdulmalik Sugow.n 2 p 34.

¹²⁷ Mugambi Laibuta. Fake news, misinformation and the coronavirus crisis.
<https://www.laibuta.com/constitution/fake-news-misinformation-and-the-coronavirus-crisis/>

¹²⁸ Ibid

¹²⁹ Ibid

¹³⁰ Ibid

¹³¹ Benesch, S. (2014) Countering Dangerous Speech to Prevent Mass Violence during Kenya’s 2013 Elections, Dangerous Speech Project, <https://dangerousspeech.org/countering-dangerous-speech-kenya-2013/> (accessed 29 July 2017)

ethos that allow individuals to aspire for the good, noble and moral probity in communication. This makes the argument that individual self-regulation could work where laws are inadequate.

The following section explores the regulatory frameworks that other selected jurisdictions are adopting.

3.5 Alternative Regulation of Social Media in other Jurisdictions

Contrary to any perception from media reports of increasing laws, most countries are trying to censor with a light hand. China and Germany, for example, have retrenched from an apparently hardened attitude to censorship. In other words, while there may be more laws, the laws are not necessarily being enforced with the rigidity that a plain reading would suggest. Governments seem aware that the controls on the internet are limited. Further evidence of the light-handed approach generally is that most countries have decided not to hold internet access providers (IAPs) liable for material that may be deemed illegal in the country. Governments seem aware that to rule otherwise would be to stifle the development of the Internet.¹³² The following examples demonstrate many jurisdictions around the world are adopting to regulate harmful social media content.

Some attempts to regulate the internet have sprung out of studies to rationalize laws in:

a) Australia

Australia's response to the proliferation of fake news is focused on countering foreign interference during elections. This was set up in the backdrop of growing concerns of potential Chinese interference and 2016 Russian interference in US elections. A task force was created called the Electoral Integrity Assurance Task Force and led by the Home Affairs Department to strengthen cybersecurity.¹³³ Two key frameworks are under discussion - the Fake News code¹ and the News Media Bargaining Code. The News Media Bargaining Code is highly controversial from the perspective of copyright and competition law, as it forces big companies such as Google and Facebook to realign market power by sharing multi-million-dollar revenues with newspaper and

¹³² *BNA Daily Report for Executives* (17 October 1996). European Commission Eyes Internet Regulations A4.

¹³³ Archit Lohan. Countering Disinformation and Hate Speech Online: Regulation and User Behavioural Change. <https://www.orfonline.org/research/countering-disinformation-and-hate-speech-online/>

media companies for using their news content, to aid their financial futures.¹³⁴ Among the strictest penal provisions (in terms of fines) against extremist content - the Abhorrent Violent Material Act, 2019 - make tech executives liable for imprisonment up to three years and fines for the platform can run up to 10 percent of a company’s global turnover.¹³⁵

b) France

French President Emmanuel Macron stated in November 2018, “if we do not regulate Internet, there is the risk that the foundations of democracy will be shaken.”^[75] France applies broadcasting standards for TV and radio stations to social media through the Higher Audiovisual Council (CSA), the independent media regulator. It aims to assure broadcasting communication freedom in the country and has been tasked with the responsibility of enforcing state policies on fake news and hate speech.¹³⁶ France has had a strict Hate Speech law in effect since 2005 and has passed a stricter legislation for online application against hateful speech (*Lutte contre la haine sur internet- An Act to Combat Hateful Content on the Internet- Avia law*)—it requires social media platforms to take down objectionable content within 24 hours of being notified. Once a political party, public authority, or an individual has filed a specific request, a judge is authorized to act “proportionally” but “with any means” to halt the dissemination of the fake news in question.¹³⁷

c) Singapore

Singapore’s POFMA Act is arguably one of the most comprehensive misinformation laws globally. It is widely criticized by human rights groups and free speech advocates due to its vulnerability to governmental interference.¹³⁸ POFMA covers “false facts” or “misleading statements”, but not satire, parody, opinions, and criticisms.¹³⁹ Under POFMA, various directions can be issued to platforms and users before dispensing fines and imprisonment. These directions include the following:¹⁴⁰ (i) Correction Direction: the party who communicated the falsehood is tasked to issue a public notice stating the false nature of information.¹⁴¹ The notice is published in

¹³⁴ Ibid

¹³⁵ Ibid

¹³⁶ Ibid

¹³⁷ Ibid

¹³⁸ Ibid

¹³⁹ Ibid

¹⁴⁰ Ibid

¹⁴¹ Ibid

a newspaper or a designated area on the platform. (ii) Stop Communication Direction: the publisher is directed to ensure the information is no longer available for proliferation, with the direction being published in a government gazette. (iii) Targeted Correction Direction: the platform is directed to send a correction notice to all end-users who accessed the falsehood. (iii) Disabling Direction: the internet service provider is directed to disable access to the falsehood.¹⁴²

3.6 Conclusion

This chapter set out to examine the adequacy of Kenya's existing legal framework for regulation of social media. Its main concern is how regulation will enhance respect for and promotion of the fundamental freedoms of speech, access to information and free media as guaranteed under Sections 33, 34, 35 and 24 of the Constitution of Kenya. It has established that freedom of expression, free media and access to information are guaranteed under international human rights law and limiting them can only be sanctioned in very limited instances. Social media has become the affordable and more accessible mode of communication between the hitherto those marginalized by traditional media and it has become a robust way that ordinary citizens engage their government and speak to power.

It has also been established that the use of social media has the potential to distort democratic outcomes, such as elections, such as what happened to Kenya's 2013 and 2017 elections, when fake news was deployed to distort the outcomes of the elections. Kenya currently does not have an adequate mechanism for regulation of social media to minimize the impact of negative fake news. The efforts that Kenya has undertaken in the recent past of passing laws for regulation of fake news are not appropriated in safeguarding a vibrant operation of the social media as well as ensuring the promotion of the freedoms stated herein. It has also established that there is a need to adopt regulatory approaches, such as the ones being used in some jurisdictions, to ensure a balance between curbing harmful fake news on elections and respecting fundamental right of freedom of expression.

¹⁴² Ibid

CHAPTER FOUR

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusion

This study has established that social media platforms facilitate the sharing of information and enhance connectivity and civic engagement. At the same time, however, they are vulnerable to abuse by malicious actors who use the channels to spread fake news and divisive content. Social media platforms may have democratized the internet, but the same technology can create conflicts as it enables the proliferation of erroneous information at an unprecedented pace. This happened in Kenya, as witnessed during the 2013 and 2017 general elections when the voters were manipulated through social media, which directed voting patterns and trajectories. This has negative impact on the democratic processes and on peoples' free will to exercise their political choices. The misuse of social media platforms can have economic, psychological, and political impacts, both online and offline, and can lead to discrimination and even violence, as indeed it has had on Kenyans during and after elections. As rightly noted by Archit Lohan, behind the veil of protecting free speech, they have encouraged negative elements, including, extremist, hateful or fake content. Tech companies in Kenya remain oblivious to such potential misuse or display inertia in finding workable solutions to the menace. Of significance is the fact that in Kenya, social media platforms are not liable under any rules or regulations. They function under a regulatory vacuum and are not bound by any industry regulatory standards for the functions they dispense. None of existing news agency regulations, consumer protection laws, data privacy or other traditional sectoral regulations apply to these intermediaries.

Due to the negative impact that fake news have had on elections in the country, Kenya has been grappling with modes of regulation to curb the menace. Most legal approaches are inadequate, in view of the fundamental freedoms of expression, free media and access to information entrenched in the constitution. In some extreme cases, there have been knee-jerk government reactions such as total internet shutdowns. The use of mostly criminal laws is an inadequate measure for regulation of social media. The Computer Misuse and Cybercrimes Act which criminalizes false publication of communications and communications has drawn the ire of human rights activists who argue

that the law has the potential to violate the fundamental freedom of expression. There is no alternative structure of governance where the Kenyan government and platforms can develop a regulatory system which is responsive to evolving platform harms, like has happened in a number of countries, some examined in chapter three of this study. An initiative of this nature should respect the central role that platforms play in facilitating the right to freedom of expression.

World over, self-regulation is being preferred for fake news regulation. Countries such as France, Australia, Germany, Singapore among others have adopted self-regulation mechanisms that avoid draconian approaches such as criminalization. Kenya could greatly benefit from these countries.

4.2 Recommendations

1. The Government of Kenya should put in place a legal framework against problematic social media content and in any such strategy, the tech platforms are bound to play the biggest role. There should be continuous collaborative engagements within the industry, along with state and non-state actors. This can enable the creation of voluntary multi-platform and multi-stakeholder initiatives. The code of ethics and voluntary audits are another welcome by-product of these collaborative measures.
2. A limited but necessary legislative support could help generate consensus with a much more effective regulatory mechanism. As discussed in chapter three, countries like France and Germany have pre-defined the limited scope of government role to avoid any arbitrary intervention and have even appointed independent regulators or independent judicial members to dispense moderation objectives. Fake News and Hate Speech codes must be founded, and authorities must explore the scope of an independent regulator. The regulator's objectives should be to assist the application of government policies and serve as a forum for redress against the platforms for arbitrary takedowns. The regulating body by design must not be subjected to governmental or platform discretion that can have the potential to be selective, arbitrary, non-transparent, and utilized to smother dissent or the genuine exercise of freedom of speech.

3. To effectively safeguard against and mitigate the impacts of ill-speech, Kenya should have better fact-checkers and authorities committed to respond to public interest. Real-time takedowns can have a positive impact as it significantly develops resistance and reduces impact of misinformation to percolate into local, deeper, and different forms.

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